

Italy| One Health Surveillance | Shiga-toxin producing *Escherichia coli*

Background & objectives

- Integrate STEC WGS data from humans, food, feed, and animal samples for One Health surveillance of STEC infections
- Establish collaboration between public health and veterinary laboratories, as well as local and central authorities

Outcomes & Impact

- Development and implementation of an IT platform on the IRIDA-ARIES infrastructure for STEC, including an automatic cluster detection and user notification system
- Inclusion of regional users from nine regions working in human clinical laboratories, official control and food, as well as from local health authorities.
- A One Health annual workshop was organized

Lessons learned

- The cluster identification was sensitive and specific, and the automatic user notification proved useful for all the stakeholders to be informed in real-time
- The IT platform does currently not allow to connect with other users to exchange information or specific requests, supporting a more efficient cluster assessment. This is currently under development
- For the system to work and to be accepted, the IT infrastructure needs a very low learning curve and with intervention of the operators reduced to a minimum

Core messages

- WGS data are easily integrated and being natively digital, allow automatic inference and unsupervised dissemination of the information on the identification of signals
- Education is crucial to overcome the resistance towards centralized approaches to data integration and to demonstrate the usefulness of approaches based on the WGS